

Institutional Instrumentalization and Democratic Backsliding in India under the Rule of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP)

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Abstract

India, long celebrated as the world's largest and most vibrant democracy, is witnessing a troubling erosion of its democratic foundations under the rule of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP). This paper critically examines the extent to which the BJP has engaged in institutional instrumentalization—strategically leveraging state institutions to consolidate power and undermine core democratic norms and principles. Central to this analysis is the BJP's manipulation of institutional frameworks to serve partisan interests. Tactics include the appointment of ideologically aligned judges to the judiciary, the suppression of dissent through media control and censorship, and the centralization of authority to reshape state institutions. The paper explores how these mechanisms have enabled the BJP to dominate public discourse, particularly through its command of social media and narrative framing around key national issues. Further, the study investigates the BJP's influence over civil society, the bureaucracy, and political opposition, revealing a pattern of democratic backsliding marked by the erosion of civil rights, the weakening of civil liberties, and the rise of authoritarian tendencies. The party's embrace of religious nationalism—often framed as a matter of national security—has contributed to growing intolerance, with freedom of speech, press freedom, human rights, and minority protections increasingly under threat. In conclusion, this paper reflects on the long-term implications of these developments for the future of Indian democracy, raising urgent questions about the resilience of democratic institutions in the face of majoritarian rule and ideological consolidation.

Keywords

India; institutions; democratic deficits; Right Wing Hindu Nationalism; Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP)

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Introduction

India's claim of *biggest democracy* and *mother of democracy* under the rule of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) has become a debatable topic. Despite these claims, India under the BJP has been labelled as an electoral autocracy (Biswas 2021). In 2023 the *Surat* court sentenced Rahul Gandhi, a leader of the opposition party Indian Congress, to two years imprisonment over his comments on Prime Minister Modi. The sentence, together with the fast-tracked disqualification of Mr. Gandhi's status as a member of parliament show the nature of the ruling party (Vishwanath 2023), which is ready to go to any extent to advance their *Hindu nationalist* political ideology and to stay in government. Having these two elements as priorities, it should be clear that democracy automatically takes a backseat under the BJP rule. There are multiple cases that give some perspective on the BJP style of governance and its undemocratic attributes. This article, however, is more interested in accessing the instrumentalization of the institutions to stronghold the position of BJP by targeting opposition, media, scholars, and individuals.

Although the BJP is classified as a right-wing party, it would not be wrong, given its attributes, to classify it as a far-right political party. For observers of Indian politics, it should be clear the BJP resembles white nationalism in the US, Bolsonarismo in Brazil (Nunes 2022), and the religious-ethnic majoritarianism of the AKP under Erdogan (Bigelow 2022). They examined the selective use of progressive terms such as "decolonization" and "indigeneity," as well as the portrayal of Hindutva as a protective response to threats encountered by peaceful Hindus (Sundaram 2022). It is intellectually sound and politically advantageous to view Hindutva as comparable to other types of far-right movements around the world that are present in democracies. The recent activities of BJP have created not only the societal disturbance because of its polarization-based politics but also has created the unnatural practices of democratic institutions. The investment that India has made in the last six decades to strengthen its institutions is losing its rhythm due to their politicization.

This paper builds its arguments and draws its conclusions using two approaches. First, it starts from the assumption that there is an exponential socio-political polarization in India after 2014 (Sahoo 2020; Neyazi 2017; Borah & Singh 2022; Dash et al. 2022). Second, it uses analyses of the strategic discourse and observations of the non-linear changes in India's democratic environment.

Decoding political polarization and democratic backsliding

Many democracies around the world have grappled with, or are currently grappling with, the challenges posed by the onset of pernicious polarization, which results in the division of society into mutually distrustful political camps in which political identity becomes a social identity. A group of researchers used the Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) data set to examine episodes of pernicious polarization worldwide since 1950 and trace their relationships to levels of democracy (The V-Dem Institute, 2022). The results are not encouraging. Severe polarization is associated with serious democratic decline: of the fifty-two instances in which democracies reached pernicious levels of polarization, twenty-six—nearly half of the cases—saw their democratic rating lowered (Somers et al. 2021). As a result, the global rise of political polarization has prompted analysts to consider a fundamental question: what long-term effects will polarization have on democracy? (McCoy 2022). Existing evidence provides plenty of cause for concern. Deep political divisions at the elite level have hampered legislative compromise, eroded institutional and behavioral norms, and incentivized politicians to pursue their goals outside of gridlocked institutions, including the courts. The polarization has three main facets.

Politicians Divide: People in extreme polarization feel disconnected from and suspicious of the "other" camp. At the same time, they are loyal to and trusting of their own camp, without questioning their biases or the veracity of their information. As a result, they are vulnerable to political leaders' rhetoric aimed at generating votes based on fear of the "other." Although this is a common phenomenon that social psychology has long recognized, it has become even more pronounced in the age of social media, 24-hour news cycles, and more politicized media outlets that repeat and amplify political attacks (McCoy and Somer 2019).

Oppositions React: Polarization, on the other hand, is a two-way street. The second factor explaining the impact of polarization on democracy is how the political opposition reacts. If the opposition responds to the bitter rhetoric and winner-take-all tactics with similar political hardball and demonizing language, they risk perpetuating a cycle that will entrench polarization politics (McCoy 2019).

Polarizing Rifts: When countries polarize around rifts that reflect unresolved debates dating back to the time of the country's formation, the polarization is likely to be long-lasting and harmful. These schisms are frequently centered on issues of national identity and citizenship rights. This kind of polarization is especially harmful because it revolves around debates about who is a legitimate citizen and who can legitimately represent them (Somer and McCoy 2019).

Thus, India's decline of democracy is the outcome of socio-political polarization that the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) has seeded after 2014.

Overview of the Indian democratic system

India is arguably the world's largest democracy, with over 1.3 billion people eligible to vote. India's democracy is a federal system, with a complex structure of government. The parliament is bicameral. India's political structure is in part based on the British Westminster system. It comprises a president serving as head of state, a prime minister leading the executive branch, a parliament with an upper and lower house (*the Rajya Sabha and Lok Sabha*), and a supreme court presiding over the judiciary. India's democracy is a product of its history and culture. India has a long history of democratic government, dating back to the time of the Mahabharata. India's culture is based on the concept of *dharma*, which includes the ideas of social order and responsibility. The Hindu concept of reincarnation also encourages people to think about the consequences of their actions on future lives. These concepts have helped to create a culture of responsibility and accountability in India, which has helped to support democracy. Caste still plays a significant role in politics, despite the fact that caste discrimination was outlawed by the Indian constitution and that early governments implemented quotas to ensure more equitable employment and educational distribution. Political parties continue to court castes of people who prefer to vote in blocs in some areas (Outlook India 2022).

The Indian Constitution plays a crucial role in supporting democracy. The Constitution is, in black and white, one of the longest in the world, and it lays out the structure and functions of the government. It also includes protections for civil rights and liberties. The Constitution has been amended numerous times to reflect the changing needs of Indian society. But the rise of the BJP also suggests that religion has been embedded into the political system of India. During the 1975 emergency, India's constitution was amended to refer to it as a secular state; a subsequent judicial decision determined that India has been secular since independence (Roychowdhury 2022). But it is well known that India is a profoundly religious nation, with people of many different religions living there. The constitution is secular in that it forbids discrimination against people based on their religion, but it does not expressly distinguish between church and state in the manner of the US constitution.

After independence, the Indian Congress Party held a dominant position in central-level politics. Using internal political practices, Indian democracy is often described as a 'congress system' (Kothari 1964). Therefore, the current attempt to challenge the constitution and democracy can be seen as an effort to transfer the congress system into the 'BJP system'.

Indian governments in the past have also made efforts to promote democracy abroad. The Indian government has been a leader in the promotion of democracy and human rights, and has provided training and support to democratic movements around the world. Despite its many successes, India's democracy is not perfect; especially under the rule of the BJP, it has been losing its democratic values and freedoms. India has a number of problems, including poverty, corruption, and religious and ethnic violence. The Indian government under the BJP has been unable to address these problems effectively. The failure of democracy in India to achieve the same level of long-term economic growth experienced by its neighbors such as China over the past 40 years may be its greatest obstacle (Price 2022). Additionally, it has not been able to end extreme destitution. The poorest residents of India lead entirely different lives from the educated elites in more globalized cities like Delhi and Mumbai. Therefore, the rise of Modi in 2014 was attributed to the unfulfilled promises of previous Indian governments.

BJP and institutional instrumentalization

Although there are various dynamics involved, while analyzing institutional instrumentalization from a broader perspective, one can approach it in three ways. First, the politicization of courts. Since 1990, the Supreme Court of India has significantly increased its authority and stature, gaining the moniker "the most powerful court in the world" (Sebastian 2019). After coming to power in 2014, the first attempt by the BJP to intervene with the procedure of the court was to interfere in the appointment of a supreme court judge. Soon after, the government amended the Constitution to establish the "National Judicial Appointments Commission" (NJAC), which allows the government to choose members of the commission that ultimately appoints judges.

On the other hand, in the past few years the judgements of courts have sparked a huge debate about the neutrality of the court and the judges. High-profile political cases, such as the Loya case, created a big controversy (Outlook India 2018). The case involved questions raised regarding the passing of CBI judge B.H. Loya, who was hearing the Sohrabuddin encounter case, in which BJP leader Amit Shah was accused of conspiring (The Indian Express 2018). In addition to dismissing the petitions calling for an independent investigation into judge Loya's passing, the court came to the firm conclusion that he perished of natural causes. Likewise, there are other notable examples, such as the Rafale case (The Hindu 2022) and the Aadhaar Act as a Money Bill case (Datar & Unnikrishnan 2018) that directly suggest the involvement of the BJP government in controversial decisions. In both cases, the court made pro-government verdicts. As mentioned above, the verdict on the Rahul Gandhi defamation case also seems politically motivated (BBC 2023).

Second, the instrumentalization of the Unlawful Activities Prevention Act (UAPA). This law has existed in India since 1967, but an amendment of the law in 2019 allowed the government to book anyone under suspicion without following the regular legal procedure. Under this act, the government has arrested human rights activists, comedians, journalists, fact checkers, and filmmakers. Under the Act, the central government may designate an organization as a terrorist organization if it: (i) commits or participates in acts of terrorism, (ii) prepares for terrorism, (iii) promotes terrorism, or (iv) is otherwise involved in terrorism. The Bill additionally empowers the government to designate individuals as terrorists on the same grounds.

This law also empowers the National Investigation Agency (NIA) to seize property, arrest individuals based on mere suspicion, and shut down organizations. It is notoriously difficult to grant bail to those detained under the law, which means that those who are accused may spend years in pre-trial detention. Father Stan Swamy, an 84-year-old Jesuit priest with Parkinson's disease who was arrested for allegedly supporting anti-national activity, died in custody after being repeatedly denied bail, even on medical grounds, in one of the most dramatic instances (The Frontline 2022). Until 2021, since the BJP came into power, 10,500 individuals have been charged under this law (Doshi 2021).

Third, the use of government agencies such as the Enforcement Directorate (ED) and the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) to manage opposition parties. Recently, in an effort to challenge the alleged use of central investigating agencies in arresting opposition political leaders and other citizens who were exercising their fundamental rights to disagree with the current union government, fourteen political parties filed a petition with the Supreme Court (Sharma 2023). Raid-related actions, such as complaints made in response to searches, have decreased from 93% in 2005–2014 to 29% in 2014–2022. Although the number of cases filed by the ED under the Prevention of Money Laundering Act, 2002 (PMLA) has increased exponentially, only 23 convictions have been obtained to date. Similarly, 43 (about 60%) of the 72 political figures the CBI investigated between 2004 and 2014 belonged to the opposition at the time. This number has now increased to over 95%. The same trend can be seen in the investigations conducted by the ED, where opposition leaders now make up 95% of all politicians under investigation, up from 54% prior to 2014.

Therefore, the BJP's tenure has witnessed a weakening of democratic institutions and checks and balances. The erosion of the independence and autonomy of institutions like the judiciary, the election commission, and the central bank raises concerns about the concentration of power in the hands of the executive. The appointment of politically aligned individuals to crucial positions undermines the objectivity and impartiality of these institutions.

Instruments used in the process

Media Control and Freedom of Press. The BJP has been accused of controlling the media to further its political agenda, of censoring and suppressing news that do not align with its goals, as well as of manipulating the content of the news (Aryal and Bharti, 2022; Yadav, 2023). It has also been accused of using its control of the media to spread false information and propaganda in order to sway public opinion. The BJP has used several methods to gain control of the Indian media. One of the most effective methods has been the use of “carrot and stick” tactics. The party has used both incentives and punishments to influence media outlets and journalists. The incentives have included monetary rewards for favorable coverage, while the punishments have included threats of legal action and denial of access to government functions. The BJP has also used its power to influence the appointment of editors and journalists in media outlets (Goel, 2020). This has allowed the party to ensure that news coverage is favorable to its agenda. Furthermore, BJP has used its control of advertising to influence media outlets. By providing or withholding advertising funds, the party has been able to influence the coverage of certain topics.

This has had a number of significant consequences. Most importantly, it has led to a decrease in both the diversity and the quality of news coverage. This has resulted in a decrease in the public's trust in the media, as well as a decrease in the public's understanding of important political issues. Furthermore, the party's control of the media has resulted in a decrease in the public's engagement with politics (Farrer, 2022). If the BJP continues to maintain its control of the media, this could have long-term implications for the country's political landscape and public discourse.

Centralization of Power. The BJP's centralization of power in India has been seen as a major step in the party's efforts to consolidate its control over the country. It has been widely criticized for its disregard for the country's constitution, its curtailing of civil liberties, and its undemocratic practices. The BJP's centralization of power has had a number of effects on India's democracy, economy, and social order (Chhibber, 2021). The party's use of its majority in the Parliament to push through controversial legislation and its attempts to silence dissent have been seen as a direct attack on the country's democratic institutions. The party has also been accused of using its power to influence the judiciary and manipulate the electoral process (Daniel, 2014). The party has also pursued a number of controversial economic policies, including the demonetization of high-value currency notes in 2016 and the implementation of the Goods and Services Tax in 2017. These policies have been seen as having a negative impact on the country's economy. The BJP's centralization of power has had a significant impact on India's social order. The party has been accused of pursuing a Hindutva agenda, which seeks to promote Hinduism and its values in the country. This has resulted in an increase in communal tensions and violence against religious minorities in India. The party's disregard for the country's constitution, its curtailing of civil liberties, and its undemocratic practices have been seen as a threat to the country's democratic institutions (Ozturk 2021).

Weakening of Oversight Mechanisms. Since the BJP came to power in India, in 2014, there have been concerns about the weakening of government oversight mechanisms. There is evidence that the BJP has been attempting to undermine the independence of key oversight institutions, such as the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) and the Reserve Bank of India (RBI). In December 2018, the RBI governor, Urjit Patel, resigned after the government interfered in the appointment of the deputy governor (Chandran, 2018). There have also been reports of the government pressuring the RBI to relax lending restrictions and to provide more financial support to troubled state-owned banks. The CBI has also come under pressure from the government. In October 2018, the CBI director, Alok Verma, was removed from his position after he launched an investigation into a corruption scandal involving several BJP ministers (Majumdar, 2019). Verma was reinstated by the Supreme Court in January 2019, but he was then removed from his position for a second time in February 2019.

There have also been other incidents in which the BJP has been accused of interfering in the work of independent institutions. In March 2018, the head of the National Statistical Commission, resigned after the government refused to publish the commission's report on the unemployment rate (The Hindu, 2019). In April 2018, the head of the Central Board of Film Certification was replaced after the release of a film that was critical of the BJP (Vetticad 2025). The BJP has also been accused of using its majority in the parliament to pass legislation favorable to its interests. In December 2018, the parliament passed a bill that allows the government to seize the property of individuals accused of corruption. The bill was opposed by the opposition parties, but it was passed with the support of the BJP. The trend of the BJP weakening government oversight mechanisms has serious implications for India (Press, 2013). It could lead to an increase in corruption and financial instability. It could also damage India's reputation as a democracy.

What is backsliding in Indian democracy?

Democratic backsliding has been the new phenomenon of world politics over the last 10-15 years. Due to the rise of right or far-right political ideology in many parts around the world, the democratic values has been challenged by these political forces. Previous studies of democratic backsliding have identified three main patterns: grievance-fueled illiberalism, opportunistic authoritarianism, and entrenched-interest revanchist (Carothers and Press, 2022). In instances of illiberalism motivated by

grievances, a political figure will mobilize a grievance, assert that the political system in place is maintaining the grievance, and claim that in order to correct the fundamental wrongs, democratic norms and institutions must be destroyed. If we analyze the rise of the BJP and the characteristics of Modi, the first and second tactic has been widely practiced in India.

Under Prime Minister Narendra Modi, India is becoming increasingly authoritative in nature, where questioning the act of Mr. Modi has been levelled and treated as a crime. On 17 January 2023, BBC broadcasted a documentary titled 'India: The Modi Question' (Ellis Petersen, 2023) The documentary claimed to be based on the unpublished report prepared by the British Foreign Office. As a reaction, the BBC offices in Delhi have been searched by Indian revenue authorities. Just a few weeks before, India banned a BBC film accused of denigrating Prime Minister Modi. The temporal proximity of the two events raises questions regarding a possible causal relation between them. The once-lively Indian press is now under intense pressure from Modi's Hindu-chauvinist movement. Journalists are being monitored and imprisoned, and the government is using coercive measures against media organizations to ensure favorable coverage (Srivastava and Agrawal, 2021). New revisions to the legislation governing digital media were introduced in January, giving the government the power to censor any content it chooses (Poddar, 2023).

The pro-democracy organization Freedom House downgraded India's classification from "Free" to "Partly Free" for the first time since the late 1990s, due to the country's waning defense of civil liberties (Freedom House, 2021). India was also downgraded to the category of "Electoral Autocracies" in a second study, by the Varieties of Democracy Institute, according to which it is no longer considered to be an "Electoral Democracy." The conclusion of the study is a damning indictment. The report claims that Modi and his party are tragically pushing India toward authoritarianism rather than acting as a champion of democracy practice and a counterweight to authoritarian influence from nations like China. The Indian government immediately attacked the report as "misleading, incorrect, and misplaced," dismissing criticism from the UN and Amnesty International, which was compelled to close its office in the nation (Ayyub, 2021).

The atrocities against minorities, especially Muslims, are also worrisome for Indian democracy. Two hundred million Muslims, one of the largest Muslim populations in the world, call India home, even though they are a minority in the primarily Hindu nation. Despite constitutional safeguards, Muslims in India have consistently experienced prejudice, violence, and discrimination. Under the direction of Prime Minister Modi and the BJP, which has promoted a Hindu nationalist agenda ever since being voted to power in 2014, anti-Muslim sentiments have increased. Just to reiterate, Prime Minister Modi has lived quite a controversial term as the Chief Minister of the state of Gujarat, being often called the 'Butcher of Gujarat' for his actions during the 2002 Gujarat riots (Jaffrelot, 2024) After Modi was elected again in 2019, the government has promoted divisive policies, which his opponents claim are meant to deny millions of Muslims their right to vote (Maizland, 2022). Violence against Muslims has increased under Modi. The actions have sparked protests in India and garnered criticism from around the world.

Since the establishment of Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS), a paramilitary group that mimics Nazism-Mussolini-ism and that PM Modi was part of, they have been claiming India as a land of Hindu, arguing that the Muslims have no place here (Frayer & Khan, 2019; Srivastava, 2017). The Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA), passed by the Modi administration, gives non-Muslim immigrants from Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan a quick route to Indian citizenship. This was perceived as an effort to introduce a "religious test for Indian citizenship" that would essentially exclude Muslims in conjunction with a planned National Register of Citizens (Sen 2022).

Under the BJP's rule, there has been a growing trend of suppressing dissent and curbing freedom of expression. This is evident through the use of laws such as sedition, defamation, and hate speech regulations to target critics, journalists, and activists. The government has also exerted control over media outlets, further limiting the plurality of voices in public discourse. The weakening of Indian democracy can be traced in seven broader clusters.

Erosion of separation of powers. The erosion of the separation of powers in India under the Bharatiya Janata Party's rule is a worrying trend. The BJP has shown blatant disregard for the constitutional principles that protect India's democracy and has instead used its power to consolidate control and pursue its own interests. It has used its majority in Parliament to push through a number of controversial bills that have undermined the independence of key institutions (Sahoo, 2020). For example, the BJP has passed a bill that gives the Prime Minister the power to appoint the heads of India's intelligence agencies, which undermines the autonomy of these institutions. A new bill, passed in December 2023, regarding the appointment of the chief election commissioner also gave the sole power to nominate the commissioner to the Prime Minister (LiveMint 2023). The BJP has also been accused of using its power to stifle dissent. For example, the BJP has cracked down on civil society organizations critical of the government and has used the sedition law to harass its opponents (Kirchgatterer, 2023). BJP has also been accused of using its control of the media to spread propaganda and silence its critics. The erosion of the separation of powers in India under the BJP's rule is a serious threat to Indian democracy.

Diminished accountability. The BJP has been embroiled in a number of high-profile cases of corruption and abuse of power. In some cases, government officials have been caught red-handed, but they have not been held accountable for their actions. There are several factors that have led to diminished accountability in India under BJP rule (Mukerjee, 2016). Firstly, the BJP has been able to consolidate its power by winning a series of state elections. This has given the party a dominant position in the political landscape, allowing it to pass legislation with little to no opposition, something that the BJP calls 'Double Engine Government' (Rooj & Ratha, 2025). Secondly, the BJP has been able to manipulate the media to present a positive image of the party and its leaders. This has helped the party to stay in power despite its record of corruption and abuse of power. Thirdly, the judiciary in India has been politicized, and the BJP has been able to appoint judges who are sympathetic to its agenda. This has led to a number of judgments that have favored the BJP and have undermined the rule of law in India. Finally, the BJP has been able to control the bureaucracy and has used its power to award government contracts and appointments to its supporters. High-level public administration officials were also promised post-retirement political appointments (Srivastava, 2020). This has led to a proliferation of corruption at the highest levels of government. The consequences of diminished accountability in India under BJP rule are grave.

Restricted citizen participation. The impact of the BJP's policies on citizen participation in India has been profound. The restrictions on the right to protest, for example, have had a chilling effect on citizens who wish to voice their dissent. This has been compounded by the fact that the government has been quick to crack down on any perceived opposition. This has had the effect of silencing many citizens who may have previously been vocal in their criticism of the government. The most profound example is the 'Farmer Protest' and the government's crackdown on the protesters. The Indian authorities have prevented farmers from demonstrating peacefully by using threats, disproportionate force, and internet shutdowns. Since 2020, farmers from the states of Punjab and Haryana have gathered outside of New Delhi, the capital of India, to voice their requests for higher pricing for their produce (Human Right Watch, 2024). 'Force' and 'Negligence' are the strategies that the Indian

government has employed. Likewise, the introduction of the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) is another example of the government's efforts to restrict citizen participation in India. The CAA has been widely criticized for its discriminatory nature, as it targets a specific religious group and has been seen as an attempt to undermine the rights of minority communities (Ghoshal, 2019). The implementation of the CAA has had a significant impact on the ability of citizens to express themselves freely and engage in meaningful political and social activities.

Intimidation and harassment. There has been a growing body of research on intimidation and harassment in India, particularly since the rise of the BJP to power under Prime Minister Narinder Modi in 2014. For example, a study by Sharma and Jenkins (2024) found that the prevalence of gender-based intimidation and harassment in India had increased substantially since the BJP's rule, with a large majority of women in the study reporting feeling unsafe and intimidated in public places. The study also found that the levels of gender-based intimidation and harassment were higher in states where the BJP was in power. Similarly, a study by Panda et al. (2020) found that there had been an increase in the prevalence of verbal and physical intimidation and harassment against religious minorities in India since the BJP's rule. The study found that religious minorities, particularly Muslims, were more likely to be victims of intimidation and harassment.

Online surveillance and social media. The increased use of online surveillance and social media in India under the BJP's rule has caused a number of civil rights issues to arise (Pearson, 2021). Firstly, citizens' right to privacy is being violated, as the government is collecting large amounts of personal data from users without their consent. This data can then be used to target certain demographics with political messages, which could give the BJP an unfair advantage in elections. For example, the Indian government ordered social media site X to delete profiles unfriendly to the government during the first week of July 2025. After New Delhi ordered the social media platform to remove over 2,300 accounts, including two Reuters news agency names, X expressed its "deep concern about ongoing press censorship in India (Aljazeera 2025)." Furthermore, the use of social media to promote the BJP's political agenda could lead to a rise in political polarization, as those who oppose the party's views may be silenced or excluded from the conversation. Recently, the term 'Whatsapp University' became quite popular in India, referring to doctored videos, misinformation, or disinformation that is spread to millions of people to twist the truth (Grazda, 2025). Finally, the increased surveillance of online activity could lead to the suppression of dissent and the curtailing of freedom of expression, as citizens may be afraid to express their opinions online for fear of being monitored by the government. In June 2025, a university professor was arrested over a Facebook status that questioned the motives and the achievements of the government during their operation (Operation Sindoor) in Pakistan (Bhargave & Bose, 2025; Ramachandran, 2025). And this is just a tip of the iceberg.

Infringement on human rights. The BJP government has pursued a number of repressive policies that have led to a dramatic decline in human rights in India (Takhtar, 2021). One key issue has been the use of repressive legislation. The BJP has passed a number of controversial bills that have led to a crackdown on civil liberties. For example, the Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act (UAPA) has been used to target political opponents of the government. The UAPA allows the government to declare an organization "unlawful" and to prosecute its members, even if they have not committed any crime. The bill has been criticized for its vague and arbitrary provisions, which allow the government to target any organization it deems to be a threat. Likewise, the BJP has sought to restrict freedom of speech and freedom of assembly. For example, the government has introduced a number of new laws that restrict freedom of speech, including the Prevention of Communal and Targeted Violence (Access to Justice and Reparations) Bill, the National Security Act, and the Criminal Laws (Amendment) Act. These

laws allow the government to criminalize free speech and to prosecute individuals who criticize the government or its policies (Rawat, 2022). The government has also sought to restrict freedom of assembly, by imposing restrictions on the right to protest. The BJP failed to address the issue of religious intolerance, which led to the normalization of mob lynchings (Bhat et. Al, 2024), destroying the homes of Muslims (Makhal, 2023), and the suppression of religion freedom (Vaishnav, 2019).

Weakening of democratic institutions: One of the main focuses of research has been the BJP's use of the 'strongman' approach to politics, which has been seen as a way to bypass traditional democratic institutions. The rise of Modi itself from the chief minister of Gujarat to Prime Minister of India would not have been possible without him having a strong personality who can dictate in the decision-making process, a characteristic that was presented in a positive way after the 10 years in power of the coalition government. This approach has been seen as a way to consolidate power and to ensure that the BJP's political agenda is implemented. However, this approach is visibly damaging democratic institutions in India (Fiaz, 2022). The BJP's economic policies have been linked to increased inequality and a weakening of economic security for the poor. This has had a damaging impact on democratic institutions in India, leading to a weakening of the political process and a lack of accountability from the government. On the other hand, the attempt to create a personality cult of Modi requires the BJP to separate the links between citizens and institutions and to establish Modi as the only key figure for the institutions (Chacko, 2024).

Conclusion

The instrumentalization of institution by the BJP government is active in an organized way, where the media, individuals, organizations, and opposition political parties have been neutralized or shut down completely. On the other hand, BJP's attempt to implement the Chinese strategy to present India internally and externally differently has loopholes, as the issues often gets internationalised. According to the BJP narrative, India is on the path to become a Bishow Guru (world leader / teacher), and the declination of all democratic indicators certainly is not setting the narrative. Following the analyses presented here, the paper can draw two conclusions. First, there is embedded polarization that the Indian government under Narendra Modi have adopted that is causing social disturbances. Mob lynching, hooliganism and Hindu supremacy have been normalized in the Indian society and are met on a daily basis. Second, the government of India under Narendra Modi has translated political polarization as a new normal in institutions. The suspension of members of parliament to avoid debates on policy, using vaguely defined legislation to identify and set aside critical voices, and turning mass media into a cooperating media are some of the examples that validate the argument about the polarization as a new normal in Indian governance.

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